

DIFFERENCES AND SIMILARITIES BETWEEN ENGLISH AND UZBEK CASES

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Abstract: In this scientific article the similarities of the agreements in English and Uzbek also point out the differences between them. The article provides a number of examples of the importance of agreements in Uzbek and English. it is highly proved that by this article some problems, complexities of grammar will be to some extent solved. From this article not only ESL student manage to use but also native speakers of English can utilize in acquiring Uzbek in the Future.

Key words: Case, nominative case, Accusative case, dative case.

Аннотация: В данной научной статье сходство договоров на английском и узбекском языках также указывает на различия между ними. В статье приводится ряд примеров значения договоров на узбекском и английском языках. весьма доказано, что этой статьей будут в той или иной степени решены некоторые проблемы, сложности грамматики. Эту статью смогут использовать не только студенты, изучающие английский как иностранный язык, но и носители английского языка, которые смогут использовать ее для изучения узбекского языка в будущем.

Ключевые слова: Падеж, именительный падеж, Винительный падеж, дательный падеж.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu ilmiy maqolada ingliz va o'zbek tillaridagi kelishuvlarning o'xshash tomonlari ham ular orasidagi farqlarni ko'rsatadi. Maqolada o'zbek va ingliz tillarida tuzilgan shartnomalarning ahamiyatiga bir qancha misollar keltirilgan. Ushbu maqola orqali grammatikaga oid ba'zi

muammolar, murakkabliklar ma'lum darajada hal etilishi yuqori darajada isbotlangan. Ushbu maqoladan nafaqat ESL talabasi, balki ingliz tilida so'zlashuvchilar ham kelajakda o'zbek tilini o'zlashtirishda foydalanishlari mumkin.

Kalit soʻzlar: bosh kelishik, tushum kelishik, jo'nalish kelishik, qaratqich kelishik.

Cases serve to link noun or pronoun with other parts of speech via some suffixes or words. This rule is suitable for both languages except those cases of varied number, in some extent functions. Looking at precise data main four cases are included in English counted as [2]

1. Subjective Case (in ancient time it was Nominative)
2. Possessive Case (or Genitive)
3. Objective (Accusative)
4. Dative Case [2]

When it comes to Uzbek case, it will involve six ones. [1]

Nominative (bosh kelishik)

Accusative (tushum kelishki)

Genitive (qaratqich kelishik)

Dative (jo'nalish kelishik)

Locative (o'rin-payt kelishik)

Ablative (chiqish kelishik)

Accusative case In English. Accusative case is created, when one particular noun has function to be the object of verb or preposition. Jack has a burning desire to watch TV every day. TV is object of verb as it is after verb –watch [2]

In Uzbek 1. Not resembling English. There is no definite and indefinite article in Uzbek language. In Uzbek, when an object has already been known, and accurate that definite object will get suffix –ni. Suffix –ni is not used

for the subject and is unlikely to be connected with other case endings.[1]
The question forms of object (nouns or pronouns) are kimni? (whom) or nimani? (what). **For example:** “unga (nimani?)telefonni bering” va “unga (nima?) telefon bering”. “Give him the telephone” vs “Give him a telephone”[5]

Remainder cases: Ablative together with Locative are not present in English cases. Even so, those cases “purposes are executed accompanied by prepositions comprising “from, in, on, at”[5]. It is noted that Objective (Accusative or Dative) case is related to verb while Genitive (or Possessive) case comes together with noun or in some parts pronoun (meningo “zim –I myself) in a sentence. **Dative case** in Uzbek .In language dative case is studied separating from accusative case where other languages including English and German they are learnt together and called one term. **Dative case** is created with –ga, -ka, -qa suffixes. In those suffixes seem to be translated like preposition “to”[5]. With the help of this case, beneficiary is introduced, direction is demonstrated. It answers “qayerga?”, “kimnikiga?”, “where?” , “to whom?” questions.

“Singlimni uyga kiritib papkani öldirib chiqdim-da, uy vazifalarini köchirib olish uchun Oriflarnikiga kirdim”[4]

“She went **to** the door and stood in it and looked out among the tomato vines”[3]

Ablative case. This case is utilized to demonstrate root, foundation, origination. The composition of such cases are done with the help of –dan suffix which is translated into English as “from”. Besides that It answers questions like kimdan? –from whom? And qayerdan? –from where? along with nimadan? –from what?[5]

“Bringing water **from** the town pump had always been hateful work in Tom's eyes”[3]

“Lekin darsdan qaytayotganda men ham bósh kelmadimi, Orifdan boplab ôchimni oldim”[4]

All in all, cases are one the most interesting as well as necessary theme for both Uzbek and English students. The reason of that a great number of other themes are correlated to this theme such as noun, pronoun, part of speeches and so on. From this point of view, it should be concluded that in teaching cases, both teachers and students ought to keep their awareness, attention in case theme. This article can be helpful for them to carry out their aims.

References:

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